

Strain sensing of epoxy resin using porous Carbon nanotube/Graphene composite buckypaper

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Strain measurement

Traditional metal strain gauge

Graphene/Carbon nanotube Buckypaper(GCBP) strain gauge

Piezoresistive properties of the GCBPs

Figure (a). Testing of the piezoresistive properties of BPs

Figure (b). $\Delta R/R_0$ - ϵ curves of the CNT BP and GCBP.

Conclusion

These excellent strain sensing performances make it potential in the field of structural health monitoring!

In-situ strain sensing capability of GCBPs

Figure (a). Schematic representation of epoxy resin specimens sticking with GCBP and Metal strain gauge.

Figure (b). The real-time $\Delta R/R_0$ of GCBP under monotonic tensile strain

Figure (c). The real-time $\Delta R/R_0$ of GCBP under cyclic tensile strain